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Data Paper

A High-Fidelity Dataset of Surface Pressure Measurements
on Low-Rise and High-Rise Prismatic Buildings from
Boundary-Layer Wind Tunnel Tests

Version: 1.0

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Dataset Access

The datasets documented in this data paper are openly available via Zenodo as a thematically organized dataset series entitled:

A High-Fidelity Dataset of Surface Pressure Measurements on Prismatic Buildings from Boundary-Layer Wind Tunnel Tests

Due to data volume limitations, the dataset is published as four independently citable subsets:

- Part I – Low-Rise Buildings with Flat Roofs With and Without Parapets
(DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17671165>)
- Part II – Low-Rise Buildings with Mono-Pitched Roofs
(DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17737055>)
- Part III – Low-Rise Buildings with Duo-Pitched Roofs
(DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17737078>)
- Part IV – High-Rise Buildings with Square Cross-Sections and Flat Roofs
(DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17737137>)

Together, these four subsets constitute the complete dataset described in this paper. Future extensions of the dataset, such as additional building geometries, roof types, or flow conditions, may be released as separate Zenodo records under the same dataset series title.

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Citation

Users should cite:

- the specific dataset subset(s) used, and
- this data paper, which provides the authoritative dataset documentation.

Recommended citation formats are provided in the corresponding Zenodo records.

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A High-Fidelity Dataset of Surface Pressure Measurements on Low-Rise and High-Rise Prismatic Buildings from Boundary-Layer Wind Tunnel Tests

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Abstract

This data paper presents a comprehensive, high-resolution dataset of surface pressure measurements obtained from boundary-layer wind tunnel (BLWT) experiments on parametrically defined low-rise and high-rise prismatic buildings. The dataset is intended to support wind engineering research, numerical model validation, and the development and assessment of wind load provisions.

The low-rise dataset comprises 60 modular building configurations derived from six base geometries with varying plan aspect ratios and four roof types: flat roofs with and without parapets, monoslope roofs, and gable roofs. Each roof configuration is further parameterized by three variations of parapet height or roof slope, enabling systematic investigation of architectural features commonly encountered in practice. In addition, a complementary set of high-rise models with square cross-sections and slenderness ratios of $\lambda = 4, 6, \text{ and } 8$ was tested, each featuring a flat roof to isolate height and aspect-ratio effects on surface pressure distributions.

All models were tested under controlled atmospheric boundary-layer flow conditions in a BLWT. Time-resolved surface pressure measurements were recorded simultaneously at multiple locations on each model, providing raw pressure time series suitable for detailed statistical, spectral, and extreme-value analyses. The dataset includes the complete raw pressure time histories as well as a consistently derived set of reference statistics, including mean, root-mean-square, and peak pressure coefficients for all configurations.

The data are accompanied by detailed metadata describing building geometries, pressure tap layouts, flow conditions, and processing procedures, ensuring reproducibility and facilitating reuse. The openly accessible dataset provides a benchmark resource for CFD validation, wind tunnel comparison studies, and the evaluation of wind-induced loads on low-rise and high-rise buildings, thereby contributing to improved predictive models and structural design methodologies in wind engineering.

Keywords: Windtunnel Data, Low-Rise Building, High-Rise Building, Bluff Body Aerodynamics

1. Introduction

Wind-induced pressures on low-rise buildings are a critical consideration for structural safety and design. Building codes and standards have traditionally based their wind load provisions on wind tunnel studies conducted in the 1970s and 1980s [1, 2]. For example, the external pressure coefficients in ASCE 7 were derived from experiments performed “30–50 years” ago [1]. While those pioneering studies laid the groundwork, they were limited by the technology of their time. In recent decades, significant advances in pressure measurement instrumentation and data acquisition systems have enabled wind tunnel tests with far more pressure taps and higher sampling rates [3, 4]. These improvements allow researchers to capture detailed pressure fluctuations over entire building surfaces, yielding richer datasets than was previously possible.

Motivated by these technological advances, several large-scale wind tunnel campaigns have been undertaken to systematically measure wind pressures on low-rise building models and make the data publicly available. Notably, the *Tokyo Polytechnic University (TPU) aerodynamic database* provides extensive simultaneous pressure time series for a wide range of low-rise building geometries [5, 6]. This database includes numerous combinations of building breadth, depth, eave height, roof slope, and roof type, tested for multiple wind directions. In North America, a collaborative program between the *National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)* and the *University of Western Ontario (UWO)* produced a similarly comprehensive dataset. Approximately 38 generic low-rise building models (gable-roof structures of varying dimensions) were tested in the wind tunnel and the pressure records were compiled into an open aerodynamic database [4]. These two databases—the TPU and NIST/UWO datasets—represent vast repositories of wind pressure data for low-rise buildings. The TPU dataset offers a broader variety of building shapes, whereas the UWO/NIST experiments included more wind directions and denser pressure tap coverage in critical areas such as roof corners and edges [3]. Despite differences in approach, studies have shown that the peak wind load effects derived from the two databases are essentially equivalent for practical purposes [3]. In particular, Hagos et. al. [3] found “peak wind effects... differed insignificantly from each other,” lending confidence that results are robust across experimental campaigns.

The availability of such high-fidelity aerodynamic databases has opened new possibilities for both research and design. Engineers have leveraged these datasets to develop *database-assisted design (DAD)* methodologies, in which raw pressure time histories from experiments are directly used in structural analysis in lieu of simplistic code pressure coefficients [7, 4]. Early studies demonstrated that using detailed pressure databases in the design process can lead to structures that are more consistent in terms of risk and often more economical compared to designs based on conventional code-based wind loads [7]. For instance, Whalen [7] showed that “provisions which use aerodynamic databases... can result in designs that are significantly more risk-consistent as well as both safer and more economical than designs based on conventional standard provisions.” This underscores the value of comprehensive experimental data in improving wind load predictions. In parallel, efforts have been made to standardize wind tunnel testing practices internationally to ensure data quality and comparability. A notable example is the comparative program organized by the *Windtechnologische Gesellschaft (WTG)*, in which 15 different wind tunnels tested the same low-rise building model; the findings helped establish quality assurance guidelines for wind tunnel experiments [8]. Such initiatives further enhance confidence in large wind pressure databases by confirming that results are repeatable across different facilities [8].

Recent research by Kopp [9] and collaborators has further refined the understanding of wind pressures on low-rise buildings, particularly for complex roof configurations and component and cladding pressures. Kopp’s work has influenced updates to ASCE 7-16 and ongoing revisions to the ASCE 7 standard, improving provisions related to low-slope roofs and solar arrays [9, 10]. His contributions underscore the importance of high-quality experimental data and robust aerodynamic databases to inform

wind load provisions that reflect physical reality while maintaining practical applicability.

Despite the progress achieved with existing datasets, important gaps remain in the publicly available data for low-rise buildings. Past campaigns have predominantly focused on simple rectangular building forms with gable (duo-pitched) roofs, often without roof overhangs or parapets [5]. Comparatively fewer open-access datasets address other common low-rise roof configurations such as flat roofs (with or without parapets) or mono-pitched roofs. These features can significantly influence wind pressure distributions, and engineers currently rely on a sparse set of studies or conservative code estimates for such cases. To support a broader range of research and validation needs, there is a clear demand for expanded experimental data covering diverse building geometries and architectural details.

This data paper presents a comprehensive dataset of wind tunnel measurements conducted on 60 low-rise building models covering a wide range of geometric parameters and roof types. The models represent variations in building aspect ratios and include four roof configurations—flat, flat with parapet, mono-pitched, and duo-pitched—with further subdivisions by parapet height or roof slope. In addition, measurements from three high-rise slender buildings are included. All tests were conducted under controlled boundary-layer flow conditions representative of suburban terrain. The resulting database provides detailed surface pressure coefficients for each model across 32 wind directions, captured at high temporal resolution. By openly sharing this dataset, we aim to facilitate advanced analytical studies, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) model validations, and the refinement of wind load provisions in standards such as Eurocode 1 [2] and ASCE 7 [1]. In summary, this curated collection of low-rise building wind pressure data builds upon previous efforts and fills critical gaps, ultimately enabling more reliable and efficient wind design for low structures worldwide.

2. Data Paper Conception and User Guide

2.1. Purpose and Scope of the Data Paper

This manuscript is conceived as a *data paper* accompanying the public release of a comprehensive dataset of surface pressure measurements obtained from boundary-layer wind tunnel experiments. Its primary purpose is to document the dataset structure, measurement conditions, processing steps, and metadata in sufficient detail to enable transparent reuse, reproducibility, and independent analysis.

The paper is not intended to present new physical interpretations, validation studies, or design recommendations. Instead, it provides the technical context necessary for users to understand the origin, limitations, and appropriate use of the archived data. Scientific analyses, comparative studies, and interpretation of results are deliberately deferred to subsequent research publications that build upon this dataset.

2.2. Intended and Non-Intended Use

The dataset is intended for use in:

- validation and benchmarking of numerical simulations (e.g. CFD),
- comparative studies of wind-induced surface pressures on prismatic buildings,
- development and testing of post-processing, statistical, and extreme value analysis methods,
- educational and methodological studies in wind engineering.

The dataset is not intended to:

- replace full-scale measurements,
- represent site-specific wind conditions,
- be used directly as a substitute for codified wind load provisions without appropriate interpretation.

These clarifications are provided to avoid misinterpretation of the dataset and to ensure appropriate and responsible reuse.

2.3. Dataset Versioning and Future Extensions

The dataset is published via Zenodo using persistent Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs). Each thematically organized subset (Parts I–IV) represents a version-specific, citable snapshot of the data at the time of publication. Future extensions of the dataset, such as additional building geometries, roof types, or flow conditions, may be released as separate Zenodo records under the same dataset series title. Such extensions will not modify the content of the existing published datasets but will be linked through versioning and related identifier mechanisms to ensure traceability and citation clarity. Users are encouraged to cite the specific dataset subset(s) used in their work, as well as this data paper.

2.4. How to Use the Dataset

Each dataset subset is organized in a structured directory hierarchy containing:

- raw surface pressure time series,
- derived statistical quantities (e.g. mean, RMS, peak pressure coefficients),
- metadata files describing geometry, pressure tap layouts, flow conditions, and data processing parameters.

Users interested in detailed time-domain or spectral analyses should directly use the raw pressure time series. Users requiring rapid comparison across configurations may rely on the provided statistical descriptors without additional post-processing. A detailed description of file formats, naming conventions, and data structures is provided in Section 8.

2.5. User Guide and Entry Points

A typical workflow for data reuse involves the following steps:

1. Select the relevant dataset subset based on building type and roof configuration.
2. Consult the metadata files to identify geometry parameters, pressure tap locations, reference quantities, and wind directions.
3. Load the raw pressure time series or derived statistical quantities using standard data analysis tools.
4. Apply user-specific post-processing, analysis, or validation procedures as required by the research objective.

To facilitate data access and post-processing, the authors provide an openly available software toolkit specifically developed to work with the archived data format. The software supports structured access to the HDF-based data files and basic inspection and processing of the stored quantities.

- **Software name:** HDF Toolkit
- **Repository URL:** Referenced in each data-base
- **Programming language:** Python
- **Development status:** Active

The use of this software is optional; users may alternatively access the data using custom scripts or third-party tools capable of reading the provided file formats. Example data access workflows and code snippets are provided in the supplementary materials or appendices to facilitate first-time use.

2.6. Data Availability and Citation

All datasets described in this paper are openly available via Zenodo under the Creative Commons Attribution license (CC BY 4.0), permitting unrestricted reuse with appropriate attribution. Users should cite both the relevant dataset subset and this data paper in any resulting publications.

3. Wind Tunnel Configuration

3.1. Wind Tunnel

The wind tunnel is an open-type tunnel constructed following Eiffel's design principles, see Fig. 1. It is equipped with components to generate the boundary layer using the Counihan method. In particular, the trip edge, vortex generators, and the settling chamber can be adjusted to achieve the desired boundary layer characteristics.

Figure 1: Boundary layer wind tunnel at the CWE, RWTH Aachen University

4. Experimental Measurement Setup

4.1. Traversal system

At the wind tunnel outlet, a three-axis traversing system is installed, Fig. 1 which allows mounting of different probes. The axes are controlled automatically using the in-house software *WTMS*, ensuring reproducible positioning during experiments. This setup enables the generation of multidimensional velocity profiles as well as velocity measurements above the building model. To evaluate the influence of the traversing arm on the approaching flow, the arm, featuring a square cross-section of 100 × 100 mm, was extended by a mounted steel tube with an outer diameter of 20 mm. The probes are installed inside this tube, while the internal cavity accommodates the routing of cables and pressure lines. This design effectively minimizes flow interference.

Figure 2: Three-axis traversing system of the BLWT

4.2. Instruments for Velocity and Turbulence Measurement

The velocity field in the wind tunnel was characterized using a combination of pressure-based and thermal anemometry probes to cover both mean flow and turbulent fluctuations.

4.2.1. Pitot and Cobra Probes

For pressure-based velocity measurements, a Pitot tube and a Cobra probe (Turbulent Flow Instruments) were employed. The Pitot tube (Fig. 3) is connected via a 90 cm pressure line, identical to those used for the surface pressure taps linked to the differential pressure scanners described in Section 4.3.2, and measures only the longitudinal velocity component u . The Cobra probe (Fig. 3a) captures all three velocity components simultaneously, allowing a detailed characterization of the flow field in terms of both magnitude and direction. Both probes are mounted on the traverse arm (see Fig. 1), enabling synchronized measurements at identical positions, with the Pitot tube serving as a reference.

Figure 3: Comparison of velocity components measured with (a) Cobra probe and (b) Pitot probe.

4.2.2. Hot-Wire and Hot-Film Anemometry

To obtain density-independent velocity data and improve temporal resolution, hot-film and hot-wire anemometers were additionally used. Hot-film air velocity transducers (TSI Series 8455 and 8465) provided stable reference values for the mean wind speed. One probe (TSI 8455) [12] was positioned at a fixed height beside the wind tunnel outlet to ensure reproducibility, while another (TSI 8465) [13] was mounted on the traversing system alongside the Pitot tube and the Cobra probe.

The TSI transducers operate on the principle of thermal anemometry, maintaining an approximately constant sensor temperature through internal electronics. Their functionality corresponds to that of Constant Voltage Anemometers (CVA). These sensors are suitable for the accurate determination of mean flow velocities but cannot capture high-frequency fluctuations due to their response time of about 0.2 s. Pressure-based probes complement these measurements by resolving dynamic pressure variations that can be converted into velocity information, although these data remain density-dependent and are affected by damping and phase shifts within the pressure tubing.

For detailed turbulence analysis, Constant Temperature Anemometers (CTA) were used. These instruments offer frequency responses up to about 100 kHz, enabling precise measurement of velocity fluctuations and turbulence characteristics. Due to the fragility of the hot wires and the requirement for careful calibration, CTA measurements were only conducted when high temporal resolution was essential, such as for determining integral length scales using the spatial cross-correlation method (Section 5.2).

4.3. Pressure Sensoring

4.3.1. Pressure Tubing Setup

For measuring surface pressures, all models either feature double-drilled holes with a pressure inlet diameter of 1 mm and an outlet of 2 mm connected to a short steel tube (for Plexiglas surfaces), or, in the case of models manufactured using STL printing with acrylate resin, the tube connector is printed directly. These holes are connected to PVC tubing with a hardness grade of 75° Shore and lengths ranging from 90 to 120 cm. The tubes have an inner diameter of 1.3 mm and a wall thickness of 0.45 mm.

The dynamic behavior of such tubing systems is a well-known source of signal distortion in surface pressure measurements when the tube length is greater than zero [14, 15]. Besides tube length as the dominant factor, additional influences such as tube deformation, temperature, and material stiffness can further affect the response characteristics [16]. Accurate pressure measurements therefore require a correction procedure tailored to the specific tubing system. Measurement functions and their evaluation are described in Section 7.2.

4.3.2. Differential Pressure Sensors

The pressure signals transmitted through the tubing are recorded by *SenSpecial* differential pressure scanners, which convert dynamic pressure fluctuations into analog voltage outputs of 3.5 ± 2.5 V. With a response time of approximately 2 ms. Each sensor channel is regularly calibrated using an airtight pressure cylinder and a high-precision reference manometer to ensure consistent accuracy and long-term stability. For the measurements described later in Section 6, the following sensor models were used:

Model	Range [Inch H_2O]	Range [Pa]
NT1S-WS-1/1D1V6T	-1 ... +1	-248.8 ... +248.5
NT1S-WS-2.5/2.5D1V6T	-2.5 ... +2.5	-622.1 ... +622.1
NT1S-WS-5/5D1V6T	-5 ... +5	-1244.2 ... +1244.2

4.4. Data Acquisition Systems for Pressure Signals

For the low-rise building models (see Section 6.1), an earlier analog scanner system was used, in which the pressure signals were transmitted via Sub-D connectors to an NI SCXI-1140 module installed in an SCXI-1001 chassis. In subsequent measurements with the high-rise models (Section 6.2), this setup was replaced by a modern data acquisition system based on an NI 9220 module mounted in a cDAQ-9189 chassis, also using Sub-D connections. Despite the technological differences between both configurations, each enabled fully synchronous surface pressure measurements in combination with the velocity probes (Section 4.2), ensuring consistent and temporally aligned datasets.

5. Modeling the Atmospheric Boundary Layer in the Wind Tunnel

Wind flow in the natural atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) is governed by surface friction, resulting in shear flow near the ground where the mean wind speed increases with height while turbulence intensity decreases. For reliable and representative wind load determination in scaled boundary layer wind tunnel (BLWT) experiments, adherence to physical similarity principles is essential. Accordingly, the ABL simulation in this study follows the guidelines of the WtG recommendations [17, 18]. The primary objective of the modeling is to realistically reproduce natural wind conditions corresponding to the terrain roughness categories defined in Eurocode 1 [19], which specify the vertical wind profile in terms of both mean velocity and turbulence characteristics. Analysis in this report just focusses on along-wind components of the flow. Raw dataset are available for further analysis of cross-wind components.

5.1. Wind and Turbulence Profiles

To reproduce the required boundary layer conditions, the inflow of the wind tunnel was adjusted using roughness elements and flow conditioning devices (Fig. 1). The velocity and turbulence characteristics were measured with Pitot probes connected to high-resolution differential pressure scanners (Section 4.3.2) and with Cobra probes equipped with integrated pressure transducers (Section 4.2.1). The profiles were scaled according to the geometric model factor λ_{geom} to ensure similarity between the full scale atmospheric boundary layer and the wind tunnel flow (Section 5.2). The thickness of the boundary layer was adjusted so that the measured profiles extended to at least 1.5 times the height of the model roof for the target terrain category [18]. The resulting data were compared with the terrain categories (TC I–TC IV) defined in the German annex of Eurocode 1 [20], which describe the vertical distribution of mean wind speed and turbulence intensity as a function of height.

$$\frac{v_m(h)}{v_{\text{ref}}} = \alpha \left(\frac{z}{z_{\text{ref}}} \right)^\beta \quad h_{\text{ref}} = \frac{10}{\lambda_{\text{geom}}} \quad (1)$$

Here, α and β are terrain dependent parameters. The reference velocity v_{ref} in the wind tunnel can be chosen freely as long as the Reynolds number criterion $Re > 10^4$ is fulfilled for sharp edged models, and it also determines the corresponding time scale of the experiment (Section 5.2). The turbulence intensity profile is expressed analogously as

$$I_u(h) = \alpha \left(\frac{z}{z_{\text{ref}}} \right)^{-\beta} \quad h_{\text{ref}} = \frac{10}{\lambda_{\text{geom}}} \quad (2)$$

where α and β are again determined by the terrain category. The turbulence intensity must be reproduced both in its relative variation with height and in its absolute magnitude to ensure dynamic similarity between the model scale and the full scale flow.

5.2. Geometric Scaling

Reproduction of flow similarity requires accurate representation of both mean velocity and turbulence structure in spatial and temporal scales. The streamwise integral turbulence length scale L_{ux} describes the characteristic size of energy-containing eddies and, according to Eurocode 1 [20], is given by

$$L_{ux,\text{original}} = 300 \left(\frac{z}{300} \right)^\epsilon \quad (3)$$

where ϵ is a terrain-dependent exponent related to surface roughness and turbulence intensity. The corresponding length scale in the wind tunnel, $L_{ux,\text{model}}$, was determined using the spatial cross-correlation method. Two high-resolution hot-wire probes (Section 4.2.2) were positioned with adjustable spacing in the streamwise direction to measure the correlation of longitudinal velocity fluctuations. The correlation

coefficient $\rho_{1,2}(r)$ decreases approximately exponentially with probe separation r , and the integral scale follows from the exponential decay constant c :

$$L_{ux,model} = \int_0^{\infty} \rho_{1,2}(r) \, dr = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-cr} \, dr = \frac{1}{c} \quad (4)$$

The geometric model scale λ_{geom} is obtained from the ratio of the natural and wind-tunnel integral length scales:

$$\lambda_{geom} = \frac{L_{ux,original}}{L_{ux,model}} \quad (5)$$

5.3. Time Scaling

In addition to the geometric scale λ_{geom} , the dynamic similarity between the model and the full scale flow is characterized by a time scale λ_{time} . The time scaling is derived from the Strouhal number, which relates a characteristic dimension to the frequency of vortex shedding and the flow velocity:

$$S = \frac{df_w}{v_{\infty}} = \frac{d}{Tv} \quad (6)$$

Assuming equality of the Strouhal number for model and natural scale, $S_{original} = S_{model}$, the equivalent test duration in the wind tunnel can be obtained. The ratio of the characteristic dimensions $d_{original}/d_{model}$ corresponds to the geometric scale λ_{geom} , leading to

$$T_{model} = \frac{v_{top,original}}{v_{top,model}} \cdot \frac{1}{\lambda_{geom}} \cdot T_{original} \quad (7)$$

From this relationship, the time scale λ_{time} follows as

$$\lambda_{time} = \frac{v_{top,model}}{v_{top,original}} \cdot \lambda_{geom} \quad (8)$$

5.4. Frequency representation of the natural wind

A further refinement of the flow modeling is achieved by the requirement of similarity in the flow spectra. Beyond reproducing mean velocity and turbulence intensity profiles, it is essential to capture the correct distribution of turbulence energy across frequencies, since this strongly influences fluctuating wind loads on building structures.

For the frequency-dependent characterization of natural wind, Eurocode 1 [19] specifies the Solari spectrum. This spectrum defines the target shape of the power spectral density (PSD) of longitudinal velocity fluctuations as a function of the measured mean velocity and the integral length scale, ensuring that the dominant eddy sizes and their decay rates are properly represented.

$$\frac{f \cdot S_u(f, z)}{\sigma_u^2(z)} = \frac{6 f_{dim}}{(1 + f_{dim}^2)^{4/3}} \quad f_{dim} = \frac{nz}{U(z)} \quad (9)$$

5.5. Boundary Layer for Low-rise Models

For the low rise building models described in Section 6.1, the boundary layer inlet section M250-03 was employed. Integral length scales were determined at several heights corresponding to the later model position. Based on the averaged decay constant of $c = -2.5$, an integral length scale of $L_{ux,model} = 0.4$, m was obtained. The geometric model scale was set uniformly to 1:250, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Determination of integral length scales L_{ux} by spatial cross-correlation for M250-03.

Since the objective of this study was to investigate general aerodynamic behavior rather than site specific effects, the simulated atmospheric boundary layer represented terrain category II according to Eurocode 1 [19, 20]. This category corresponds to a roughness length of $z_0 = 0.05, m$, a power law exponent for the wind profile of $\beta = 0.16$ and a scaling coefficient of $\alpha = 1.0$. For the reference case at full scale, a mean velocity of $v(z = 10, m)_{Original} = 25, m/s$ was adopted, which is consistent with wind zone II as defined in Eurocode 1 [19, 20]. In the wind tunnel, the corresponding reference velocity at $z = 4, cm$ was adjusted to $v(z = 4, cm)_{model} = 7, m/s$.

The boundary layer was adjusted to ensure that the velocity and turbulence intensity profiles were fully developed over the model height. The tallest building in the test setup had a height of $h = 15.2, cm$, corresponding to a natural height of approximately 38 m. The measured profiles satisfied the required flow similarity, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Measured turbulence and velocity profile for low-rise buildings' investigations compared with different terrain categories according to Eurocode 1

Finally, the inflow turbulence was analyzed in the frequency domain using power spectral density (PSD) estimation of the longitudinal velocity fluctuations. The measured spectra were compared with the Solari reference spectrum, as shown in Figure 6. The close agreement between the experimental and

reference data confirms that the simulated boundary layer adequately reproduces the spectral energy distribution of natural wind turbulence.

Figure 6: Power spectral density of inflow velocity compared with the Kaimal spectrum, as used for the low-rise buildings

5.6. Boundary Layer for High-rise Models

For the high-rise models (see Section 6.2), the boundary layer inlet section M150-07 was used. The integral length scales were measured at several heights below the model position. It was assumed that no significant change would occur at greater heights. The averaged decay constant was determined as $c = -2.06$, resulting in an integral length scale of $L_{ux,model} = 0.49$ m. The geometric model scale was uniformly set to 1:150, as illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Determination of integral length scales L_{ux} by spatial cross-correlation for low-rise buildings

The experiments were conducted to obtain high-resolution time series of façade pressure fluctuations on tall buildings. As in the low-rise investigations, the inflow simulation did not represent a specific site but a generic flow condition corresponding to terrain category II. According to Eurocode 1 [19, 20], this category is characterized by a roughness length of $z_0 = 0.05$, m, a power-law exponent of $\beta = 0.16$, and a scaling coefficient of $\alpha = 1.0$.

The boundary layer was adjusted to ensure that both the velocity and turbulence-intensity profiles were fully developed over the model height. The tallest building model reached a height of $h = 80$, cm, representing approximately 120, m in full scale. The measured profiles indicate a mixed terrain category between II and III. The fitted velocity profile generally aligns with terrain category II but transitions from TC II near the ground to TC III at greater heights. The turbulence-intensity profile shows a similar

behaviour, supporting the interpretation of a mixed terrain roughness class according to Eurocode 1 (Figure 8).

The reference inflow velocity was selected based on the Eurocode mean-velocity profile and the time-scaling requirements. Due to the mixed characteristics of the measured profiles, the reference was chosen according to terrain category II combined with wind zone II for all high-rise models. For Models A0H4W1L1 and A0H6W1L1, the inflow speed was set to achieve a time scale of approximately 1:50, corresponding to about 12 s of full-scale time at model scale. For Model A0H8W1L1, the inflow velocity had to be reduced because structural vibrations occurred at higher wind speeds; the velocity was therefore adjusted until a time scale of 1:40 was obtained, corresponding to roughly 15 s in full scale.

Figure 8: Measured turbulence (left) and velocity profile (right) for high-rise buildings' investigations compared with different terrain categories according to Eurocode 1

The inflow turbulence was analyzed in the frequency domain using power spectral density (PSD) of the longitudinal velocity fluctuations. The measured spectra were compared with the Kaimal spectrum at different heights, as shown in Figure 9. The close agreement between the experimental and reference spectra confirms that the simulated boundary layer accurately reproduces the frequency distribution and energy content of natural atmospheric turbulence.

Figure 9: Power spectral density of inflow velocity compared with the Kaimal spectrum, as used for the low-rise buildings

6. Building Configurations

6.1. Low-rise Buildings

This study was conducted as part of the AIF project No. 15683 N/1 [21], which aimed to develop simplified load models for the global structural design of typical steel industrial halls.

To meet this objective, the experiments were carried out at a geometric scale of 1:250, chosen to match the available wind tunnel configuration (see Section 5.5).

A sufficiently broad and representative set of building geometries was required to achieve reliable and generalizable results. Therefore, variations were introduced both in the base geometry and in the roof design. Figure 10 summarizes the range of investigated parameters.

Figure 10: Overview of the considered low-rise model variants for measurements in the boundary layer wind tunnel

Combining all base geometries with the different roof types resulted in a total of 60 model configurations. Each configuration is identified by an acronym encoding its geometric parameters. The naming structure consists of four defining components, as illustrated in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Tree structure of the parameters defining the low-rise model configurations

The models were manufactured using a high-precision selective laser sintering (SLS) process, which allowed for the integration of pressure holes and tube connectors directly into the model geometry. The modular design enabled reconfiguration of measurement elements across different model variants. Figure 12 shows representative examples of the produced models.

Figure 12: Examples of low-rise building models

For wind tunnel testing, pressure measurement points were placed on those surfaces of the building envelope whose normals are parallel to the main frame plane (see Figure 13). This focus reflected the assumption that the steel frames act as the primary load-bearing structures. The gable walls were left uninstrumented to allow for a higher density of pressure taps on the other surfaces. The exact tap locations and corresponding model parameters are documented in the measurement data sheets.

Figure 13: Definition of inflow directions in the wind tunnel tests

6.2. High-rise Buildings

This study was conducted within the framework of the DFG project, which aimed to analyze pressure fluctuations on high-rise facades. In addition to low-rise industrial halls, slender high-rise buildings were examined to extend the applicability of the results to tall structures. The motivation was twofold: first, the higher boundary-layer profile achievable in the wind tunnel enabled the study of wind-induced pressures at greater building heights; second, particular emphasis was placed on the time-dependent effects of fluctuating wind loads on facades, which can contribute to fatigue phenomena in cladding elements and their connections over a structure's lifetime.

To achieve a high spatial resolution of facade pressures while maintaining compatibility with the wind tunnel setup, a geometric scale of 1:150 was selected. This ensured that both the characteristic turbulence scales and the building geometry were appropriately represented within the wind tunnel's boundary-layer depth (see Section 5.6).

Three modular high-rise models with varying aspect ratios were developed to investigate the influence of building slenderness on facade pressure distributions. Each model featured a double-symmetric base geometry, allowing only one facade to be instrumented with pressure taps while maintaining consistent resolution—equivalent to approximately 15 m² per tap in full scale—across all variants. The configurations are summarized in Table 2, and a schematic overview is provided in Figure 14.

Model	Cross-section $B : D$	Slenderness λ	Number of taps
A0H4W1L1	1:1	4	80
A0H6W1L1	1:1	6	120
A0H8W1L1	1:1	8	160

Table 2: Overview of the three modular high-rise building models with varying aspect ratios

Figure 14: Schematic overview of the modular high-rise building models

The models were manufactured from a combination of acrylic glass and aluminum using CNC machining. Acrylic glass allowed visual inspection of the internal pressure tubing, while aluminum provided the high stiffness of the main structural components, ensuring quasi-static behavior and preventing unwanted model vibrations. For additional structural support, an inner profile core was placed inside. This core was connected to the outer aluminum walls and further reinforced by an internal Aluminum profile using 3D-printed components. At the bottom of the model, this internal profile extended outside the model and was subsequently connected to the turntable plate. Connecting parts were also made of aluminum to guarantee sufficient strength and ductility. All joints were realized using countersunk screws embedded exclusively in aluminum elements to avoid interference on the measurement facade. To further minimize potential flow disturbances, all visible screw recesses were carefully sealed.

Figure 15: High-rise building models

The inflow directions for the wind tunnel testing campaign are defined as illustrated in Figure 16. The surfaces highlighted in red indicate the measurement facades which were equipped with the pressure taps.

Figure 16: Definition of inflow directions in the wind tunnel tests.

7. Measurement and Evaluation

For the preparation of the wind tunnel measurements, control files were created for each model to define the test conditions. In addition to general information, these control files also specify the assignments of individual pressure taps to the differential pressure sensors used and the type of pressure transmission. Each individual wind tunnel measurement is controlled by a configuration file that sets the essential parameters of the test and provides and documents them for later evaluation.

- Scale
- Height and type of the reference sensor
- Target wind tunnel velocity at the height of the reference sensor
- Start value, end value, and step size of the inflow angles
- Sampling rate of the pressure acquisition system
- Number and duration of storm events

The wind tunnel models are then measured fully automatically based on these control files by the self-developed wind tunnel software *WTMS*. This ensures comprehensive documentation of recording conditions for each test and that all measurements are conducted under comparable conditions.

For all models, inflow angles were varied in 11.25° increments, yielding 32 wind directions. Measurements were conducted at sampling rates between 1600 and 2000 Hz, depending on the number of active pressure sensors. For each direction, thirty storm events were recorded to ensure statistical stability within a 90 % confidence interval and a maximum underestimation of 5 % [22].

7.1. Determination of Pressure Coefficients

The measured surface pressures are recorded in physical units (Pascal). To eliminate the dependence on the reference wind velocity, the pressures at each tap are normalized by the reference dynamic pressure, resulting in dimensionless pressure coefficients c_p .

$$c_p(t) = \frac{p(t)}{q_{ref}} \quad (10)$$

The reference dynamic pressure q_{ref} can be determined using the gust factor method according to [19]:

$$q_{ref} = \frac{1}{2} \rho u_m^2 (1 + 2k_p I_u) \quad (11)$$

where u_m is the mean wind speed, ρ the air density, k_p the peak factor is defined as 3.5 to Eurocode 1 or 3.0 according to the German national Annex, and I_u the measured turbulence intensity in the wind tunnel.

An alternative method for defining the reference dynamic pressure is based on extreme value statistics of the wind speed, where the characteristic value corresponds to the 98 % quantile of the velocity distribution in accordance with Eurocode 0 [23]. If the inflow turbulence is measured using a pressure-based technique (see Section 4.2.1), the characteristic gust pressure can be derived analogously under the assumption of a Gumbel distribution.

For practical implementation, the recorded wind events from the reference probe are statistically evaluated in analogy to the procedure used for determining characteristic pressure coefficients (see Section 7.4). For each inflow direction, a representative reference pressure is obtained and used to normalize all corresponding surface pressure measurements.

7.2. Correction of the Pressure Transmission System

The transmission of pressure from the tap to the differential pressure sensor via tubing causes modifications to the original signal. With increasing signal frequency, the original signal is attenuated, and

resonance effects may also occur in certain frequency ranges. Generally, the transmission behavior is increasingly influenced by the tubing length. However, using very short or no tubing is often not feasible for practical reasons. Alternatively, a correction of the signal modified by pressure transmission through tubing can be applied. Analogous to a linear structural dynamic system under random excitation, the response of the pressure transmission system in the frequency domain is reversible. The frequency response $H(j\omega)$ is defined by the amplitude ratio and phase difference of harmonic input and output signals at all frequencies:

$$H(j\omega) = \frac{Y(j\omega)}{X(j\omega)} \quad (12)$$

The frequency response provides the necessary inverse operation, allowing correction of the measured (complex) spectrum and thus enabling calculation of the actual pressure spectrum acting at the measurement point.

For the experimental determination of the complex frequency response, both the input and output signals of a dynamically excited system must be recorded. The analytical determination of the frequency response uses correlation analysis, exploiting signal correlations to qualitatively improve the estimated frequency response. Denote the ideal signals as: $x(t)$ the input signal and $y(t)$ the output signal. Since measurements are always contaminated by noise, the measured quantities are $u(t)$ for the input signal plus noise and $v(t)$ for the output signal plus noise.

Based on these measured signals, two different frequency response functions can be defined [24]:

$$H_1(j\omega) = \frac{S_{uv}(j\omega)}{S_{uu}(j\omega)} \quad (13)$$

$$H_2(j\omega) = \frac{S_{vv}(j\omega)}{S_{vu}(j\omega)} \quad (14)$$

A key requirement for high-quality frequency response functions is a sufficient number of frequency averages, as each averaging improves the estimate of the true frequency response.

The functions H_1 and H_2 represent the upper and lower bounds of the true frequency response $H(j\omega)$. Since similar signals and sensors were used in this application, the mean of H_1 and H_2 was used.

The coherence function measures the statistical dependence of the measured power spectral densities of the input and output signals and is defined as:

$$\gamma_{uv}^2(\omega) = \frac{|S_{uv}(\omega)|^2}{S_{uu}(\omega) \cdot S_{vv}(\omega)} \quad (15)$$

Furthermore, in terms of the previously determined frequency responses H_1 and H_2 , it holds that:

$$\gamma_{uv}^2(\omega) = \frac{|H_1(j\omega)|}{|H_2(j\omega)|} \quad (16)$$

In the present study, the complex frequency response of the pressure transmission system (tubing length $s = 90$ cm) was determined by exciting a tube with a dynamic pressure signal (white noise generated by a vibrating membrane) and measuring both input and output signals with pressure sensors. A total of 100 independent measurements of duration $t = 1$ s each were conducted to obtain a sufficient data basis for spectral averaging.

Figure 17a) shows the resulting complex frequency response in amplitude and phase. Figure 17b) shows the associated coherence function $\gamma^2(\omega)$. The coherence function indicates the reliability of the correlation measurement; values closer to 1 indicate better representation of the investigated system by the identified frequency response.

The standard application of the known frequency response is to reconstruct the pressure time series actually acting on the surface based on the distorted output signals measured at the end of the pressure transmission system. This procedure is exemplified in Figures 17c-f). First, a dynamic pressure time series is applied to the pressure transmission system (again using the vibrating membrane, where the input signal can be controlled and measured) and recorded. As in the actual measurement, only one measurement is performed. Figure 17c) shows the clear difference between the input signal (reference) and the measured signal at the tube end (S90cm). The difference in the spectra is also pronounced in 17d). When the complex spectrum of the measured output signal is divided by the previously determined frequency response $H(j\omega)$, the input signal is estimated as:

$$X(j\omega) = \frac{Y(j\omega)}{H(j\omega)} \quad (17)$$

The correction result can first be seen in 17e) by the now closely matching estimated input spectrum to its experimentally determined counterpart (reference). The inverse Fourier transform yields the time-domain description of the input signal shown in 17f).

Comparison of the reference signal with the corrected output signal shows that the signal correction using the frequency response determined by correlation analysis achieves excellent accuracy and can therefore also be applied in extreme value methods within time history calculations.

Figure 17: Incorporation of the transfer function of the pressure transmission system for tubing length $S = 90$ cm.

7.3. Consideration of Tributary Areas

In the design of façades and structural components, the concept of tributary areas is essential for representing the spatial correlation of wind pressures. Each pressure tap or surface segment corresponds to a defined tributary area over which the fluctuating pressure is assumed to act uniformly. For small areas, local fluctuations dominate, while for larger areas, the effects of flow correlation and vortex coherence lead to a statistical reduction in the effective load intensity.

Eurocode 1 [19] specifies external pressure coefficients for tributary areas between 1 m² and 10 m², accounting for the influence of spatial correlation within this range. Areas around 1 m² typically represent local elements such as cladding or panels directly exposed to turbulence, whereas areas approaching 10 m² are associated with larger façade segments or substructures where partial correlation reduces the resulting pressure amplitude. For areas smaller than 1 m² or larger than 10 m², no additional correction is prescribed, implying that the correlation effect is considered constant outside this interval.

To quantify the spatial correlation of wind pressures and provide a practical approach for application in wind tunnel studies, Lawson [25, 26] developed the so called TVL formulation, based on full scale pressure measurements of a tall building by Newberry and Eaton [27].

$$\tau = \frac{T \cdot L}{V} \quad (18)$$

Here, L denotes the diagonal length of the area of interest, V the reference velocity, and K an empirical constant. Lawson derived a value of $K = 4.5$ from experimental data, representing the exponential decay parameter in the spatial coherence function of the pressure signal. The resulting averaging time τ characterizes the mean duration over which wind pressure acts simultaneously on the considered area.

Cook [28] subsequently revisited this formulation and, accounting for aerodynamic admittance effects, proposed a reduced value of $K = 1.0$. The discrepancy between these two constants has a pronounced influence on the resulting averaging time: Cook's formulation yields substantially shorter effective averaging times and therefore more conservative estimates.

To obtain realistic values of τ and the corresponding tributary areas, wind tunnel measurements with high spatial resolution are required. In practice, however, this is often constrained by scaling effects or by the limited number of available pressure channels. Pomaranzi et al. [29] therefore examined the applicability of the TVL formulation using an exceptionally high tap density over a confined façade region of a high-rise building. Their results indicate that Cook's formulation tends to be overly conservative, whereas Lawson's equation underestimates the correlation time, particularly for taps located near edges. Furthermore, they showed that no single universal value of K exists; instead, it depends strongly on the tap location on the façade and on the wind angle of attack.

In their study, the calculated values of τ were subsequently used to derive an equivalent model time by applying a moving-average filter to the pressure signals. The inverse of this time constant was also interpreted as a characteristic frequency, allowing the use of a low-pass filter with steeper roll-off characteristics instead of a broad moving-average filter.

7.4. Determination of characteristic Pressure Coefficients

Various methods have been presented historically for determining pressure coefficients. Advances in measurement technology and data acquisition have influenced how peak pressure predictions are made.

The *quasi-stationary concept* assumes structural loads are caused by an enveloping gust, with all surface pressures changing simultaneously and proportionally to the wind inflow. Peak loads are estimated by combining the mean pressure coefficient \bar{c}_{pe} with the gust velocity pressure of the undisturbed inflow. This method's main drawback appears in regions of strong flow separation, where the assumption of

similar fluctuation behavior between inflow and surface pressure fails and mean values tend to zero, preventing reliable extreme value predictions.

A significantly improved prediction method is the *peak factor method* introduced by Davenport. This method captures both mean pressures and fluctuations via standard deviations at measurement points. Extreme pressures are then predicted as the sum of the mean pressure and the standard deviation scaled by the *peak factor* g . This approach yields more realistic predictions of extremes near the windward edges. However, the choice of the peak factor is problematic, as it varies over the building surface depending on geometry and location, as shown by Cook [28].

Only with the introduction of the *extreme value method* was it possible to establish extreme pressure coefficients at all surface points on a uniform statistical safety level. By recording multiple independent data sequences, the respective extreme minima and maxima can be evaluated at a specified fractile. It has been shown that the extremes can be conservatively described by the Fisher-Tippet Type I (Gumbel) distribution function [22]:

$$F(x) = \exp \left\{ - \exp \left[-a \cdot (\hat{c} - u) \right] \right\} \quad (19)$$

Here, \hat{c} is the sought extreme pressure coefficient, u the modal value, and a the shape parameter controlling scatter. The term $a \cdot (\hat{c} - u)$ is called the *reduced variate*.

When applying the extreme value method, the question arises for which fractile the characteristic pressure coefficients should be defined. This is based on the fact that the non-exceedance probability for wind loads (combining velocity pressure and shape factor) is specified in *Eurocode 0* [23] as $p = 0.02$, and that the reference velocity pressure q_{ref} is defined with the same non-exceedance probability. Thus, it must be determined at what statistical level the coefficient must be secured to meet the required safety for the combined process.

Cook and Mayne [30] investigated this and concluded that a reduced variate of $a \cdot (\hat{c} - u) = 1.4$ corresponds to a non-exceedance probability of 78%. A more recent study by *Kasperski* [22] examined deviations of extremes from the assumed Fisher-Tippet-I distribution and the validity of the *Cook-Mayne* coefficient considering the local wind climate. The safety of the fractile value according to *Cook-Mayne* was confirmed under conditions similar to those of the present study.

In this study, the *extreme value method* combined with a reduced variate of $a \cdot (\hat{c} - u) = 1.4$ (*Cook-Mayne* coefficient) is applied both for determining characteristic pressure coefficients and characteristic structural effects.

8. Data Processing

This section describes the processing steps carried out after the wind tunnel measurements.

8.1. Migration and Transfer

In the first step, the recorded data were converted from the proprietary *TDMS* format into the standardized *HDF5* format. During this conversion, all metadata, including geometric model information, tap coordinates, and experimental setup parameters, were preserved. The resulting data structure allows centralized access and independent usability for further processing.

8.2. Preprocessing

The next stage involved correction of the tubing-induced damping and amplification effects on the raw pressure time series (see Section 7.2). Subsequently, the surface pressures were normalized to dimensionless pressure coefficients using non-exceedance probability evaluation based on the Fisher–Tippett type I distribution (see Section 7.1). If individual pressure taps were identified as defective or missing, a weighted interpolation was applied to reconstruct the corresponding pressure data. This ensured continuous spatial coverage of the façade, while distinguishing interpolated data as numerically derived rather than experimental results. To reduce potential noise and improve data handling efficiency, a low-pass FIR filter with a Blackman–Harris window and a cut-off frequency of 400 Hz was applied. The filtered signals were then downsampled by a factor of two, resulting in an effective sampling frequency of approximately 900–1000 Hz. Furthermore, the data type was reduced from *float64* to *float16*, given the limited range of c_p -values. To verify that these reduction steps did not lead to significant information loss, statistical comparisons were performed. The difference between the reduced and full-precision datasets remained below 3%, confirming the validity of the preprocessing workflow.

8.3. Postprocessing

In the final stage, statistical parameters were derived from the processed c_p -time series. Pressure coefficients were determined for tributary areas of 1 m² and 10 m² using the TVL formula with the empirical constant $K = 4.5$ as proposed by Lawson (see Section 7.3). The implementation was realized as a time-domain moving average filter.

Characteristic pressure coefficients were then evaluated according to the procedure described in Section 7.4. Due to storage limitations on Zenodo, the full processed time series were not archived; instead, only statistical descriptors were stored to represent the datasets compactly and reproducibly. Table 3 provides an overview of the statistical parameters derived during postprocessing.

Table 3: Overview of statistical parameters obtained from processed pressure coefficient time series

Parameter	Symbol	Description
Maximum	$c_{p,max}$	Maximum value within the complete time series.
Minimum	$c_{p,min}$	Minimum value within the complete time series.
Mean value	\bar{c}_p	Arithmetic mean of the pressure coefficient time series.
Standard deviation	σ_{c_p}	Statistical dispersion of pressure fluctuations around the mean.
Skewness	S_{c_p}	Measure of the asymmetry of the pressure coefficient distribution.
Kurtosis	K_{c_p}	Measure of the sharpness of the distribution peak relative to a normal distribution.

Overview of statistical parameters (continued)

Parameter	Symbol	Description
Gumbel (max)	$c_{p,G,max}$	Extreme value derived from Gumbel Type I distribution (upper tail).
Gumbel (min)	$c_{p,G,min}$	Extreme value derived from Gumbel Type I distribution (lower tail).
Peak factor (max, mean)	$g_{max,mean}$	Mean peak factor calculated for the upper envelope.
Peak factor (min, mean)	$g_{min,mean}$	Mean peak factor calculated for the lower envelope.
Peak factor (max, max)	$g_{max,max}$	Maximum observed peak factor for positive pressure fluctuations.
Peak factor (min, min)	$g_{min,min}$	Maximum observed peak factor for suction (negative) pressure fluctuations.

9. Data Archiving

The storage of the data follows the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) [31], which are intended to establish scientific standards for handling research data. In addition, the guidelines of the German Research Foundation (DFG) on the handling of research data are applied [32]. Apart from the explicitly stated limitations, no data have been withheld.

9.1. Selection of Data Format

The raw data from the wind tunnel measurements are stored in the proprietary TDMS format developed by National Instruments (NI). This binary file format was designed for efficient reading and writing of large data volumes within short timeframes. A TDMS file follows a three-level hierarchy: *File – Group – Channel*, where the file serves as the container, the group provides a structural organization, and the channel stores the actual measurement data. Each level of this hierarchy allows the inclusion of metadata related to the measurement.

However, TDMS is a vendor-specific data format primarily optimized for NI software such as LabVIEW and DIAdem. While the format is documented and accessible via third-party tools, its limited hierarchical data model and the absence of an open, vendor-independent standard restrict its suitability for long-term data exchange and cross-institutional collaboration. For this reason, the HDF format developed by the HDF Group [33] was chosen instead. This decision is based on the following reasons:

- Each structural level of the HDF format supports metadata, enabling centralized metadata management and resulting in a self-documenting file structure.
- The format supports a wide range of data types, including numerical arrays, structured data (e.g., JSON), and image data such as PNG and JPG, which can be stored as binary objects.
- Datasets can be accessed via hierarchical keys, and metadata can be read or modified without loading the full dataset into memory.
- Well-maintained API interfaces for Python and MATLAB, as well as cross-platform HDF viewers for desktop and web-based applications, are available.
- The HDF format has been actively maintained for more than 25 years, providing a high degree of long-term accessibility, stability, and sustainability.

9.2. Provided Datasets

Each wind tunnel measurement is provided as a set of three files. The dataset files are stored together in a ZIP archive using BZIP2 compression, while the datasheet is provided separately.

```
Dataset
├── <ModelName>.zip
│   ├── <ModelName>_timeseries_dataset.h5
│   └── <ModelName>_statistical_dataset.h5
└── <ModelName>_datasheet.pdf
```

The preprocessed raw data from the wind tunnel measurement are stored with the suffix *_timeseries_dataset*, whereas the evaluated statistical data use the suffix *_statistical_dataset*. In addition, each dataset includes a datasheet file that contains the measurement-specific metadata in a structured form. This includes, among others aspects:

- Model dimensions
- Aerodynamic coefficients
- Sensor and tap locations
- Model geometry (including dummy parts)
- Result visualizations of $\hat{C}_{p,10}$, $\check{C}_{p,10}$, and maximum standard deviation

9.3. Data Structure

Each HDF file follows a standardized and uniform data structure to ensure consistency and comparability across all datasets. The file is divided into two main levels: an *information level*, which contains metadata and processing parameters, and a *data level*, which stores the measured pressure time series.

9.3.1. Overall File Organization

Both levels are located at the root of the HDF file and are accessed via predefined group names to ensure consistent data access.

9.3.2. Information Level

The information level is located at the root of the file under the group `Info`. It contains all metadata, processing parameters, and supplementary datasets required for interpretation, reproducibility, and post-processing.

Calculations.

The *Calculations* group contains parameters derived during preprocessing and postprocessing and documents all calculation steps applied to the raw measurement data (see Section 8).

PreProcessing.

This dataset stores all parameters used during preprocessing of the pressure time series. An overview of the stored parameters is given in Table 4.

Table 4: Overview of **PreProcessing** parameters

Parameter	Unit	Description
ReferenceBuildingHeight	m	Reference building height.
CorFacWindspeed	-	Correction factor for wind speed if the reference probe was not positioned at the reference building height.

continued on next page

Overview of PreProcessing parameters (continued)

Parameter	Unit	Description
BasicGustVelocity	m/s	Basic gust velocity at reference height according to DIN EN 1991-1-4.
TurbIntensity	-	Turbulence intensity at reference height, derived from wind profile measurements.
TimeTargetModel	s	Calculated model-scale measurement duration equivalent to 600 s in full scale.
ScaleTime	1:x	Time scale factor corresponding to 600 s in full scale.
TargetSamplingPoints	-	Number of sampling points for the target measurement duration.
OutputDataType	-	Data type used for storage.
DownSampleDataBy	-	Downsampling factor.
DownSampledSamplerate	Hz	Resulting sampling rate after downsampling.
ReferencePressureMethod	-	Method used to calculate reference pressure for normalization of pressure time series.

CP-01 and CP-10.

These groups contain parameters used for postprocessing pressure coefficients for tributary areas of 1 m² (CP-01) and 10 m² (CP-10). Since postprocessing builds upon the preprocessing results, all preprocessing parameters are stored redundantly within these groups. Table 5 lists only the parameters introduced during postprocessing.

Table 5: Overview of **CP-01** and **CP-10** parameters

Parameter	Unit	Description
CutFrequency	Hz	Calculated cut-off frequency derived from the TVL formula.
KValue	-	Empirical <i>K</i> -value used in the TVL formula.
TargetArea	m ²	Tributary area considered for the calculation (1 m ² or 10 m ²).

Geometry.

This group contains the geometric representation of the measured wind tunnel model. The *Original* dataset stores the initial point cloud of all measurement points, which is used to generate the *Meshed* dataset by means of a Voronoi-based meshing and triangulation approach. All geometric data are provided in model scale. Both datasets are provided in tabular form and include multiple attributes, summarized in Table 7.

Table 7: Overview of geometry-related dataset attributes (prefix-based)

Prefix	Attributes	Description
Global	GlobalX, GlobalY, GlobalZ	Global coordinates of the original point cloud.
Local	LocalX, LocalY, LocalZ, LocalVertexIndex	Local coordinates, rotated into the XY-plane.
Projected	ProjectedX, ProjectedY, ProjectedZ	Projected coordinates for unfolded representation.
Is	IsMeshNode, IsMeasurementPoint	Boolean flag (0/1) to filter mesh nodes and measurement points.

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Overview of geometry-related dataset attributes (continued)

Prefix	Attributes	Description
PointID	PointID	Identifier of the measurement point or mesh node.
PlaneID	PlaneID	Identifier of the measurement plane for dataset filtering.

Metadata.

The *Metadata* group contains supplementary information required for interpretation, traceability, and reproducibility of the measurements.

DefectTaps.

This dataset lists defective pressure taps and documents the interpolation strategy used to reconstruct missing data, including weighting factors and reference taps.

Measurement.

The *Measurement* dataset contains general metadata describing the experimental setup, environmental conditions, reference values, and scaling information. An overview of all stored parameters is provided in Table 8.

Table 8: Overview of measurement metadata

Parameter	Unit	Description
Nationality	–	Relevant National Annex of EN 1991-1-4.
TerrainCategory	–	Terrain category according to EN 1991-1-4.
Windzone	–	Wind zone according to EN 1991-1-4.
WindTunnelSetupId	–	Identifier of the wind tunnel setup.
ReferenceModelHeight	m	Reference model height.
ReferenceSpeedSensorNameHeight	m	Height of reference speed sensor.
ReferenceSpeedSensorName	–	Type of reference speed sensor (e.g. Prandtl).
ModelScale	1:x	Geometric scale of the wind tunnel model.
RelHumidity	%	Relative humidity during measurement.
Temperature	°C	Air temperature during measurement.
AtmosPress	hPa	Atmospheric pressure during measurement.
TubeLength	cm	Pressure tube length.
Nstorms	–	Number of synthetic storm events.
DataName	–	Dataset name / identifier.
Samplerate	Hz	Sampling frequency.
NumberOfStormEvents	–	Number of storm events in dataset.
MeasurementLength	s	Total duration of one measurement.
RotationalAngleIncrement	°	Increment of model rotation per step.
FirstRotationalAngle	°	Starting angle of model rotation.
LastRotationalAngle	°	Final angle of model rotation.
AirDensityMoist	kg/m ³	Air density incl. humidity.
AirDensity	kg/m ³	Dry air density.
ReferenceMeanWindSpeedUncor	m/s	Uncorrected reference mean wind speed.
ReferenceMeanWindSpeedCorFac	–	Correction factor for reference wind speed.
ReferenceMeanWindSpeed	m/s	Corrected reference mean wind speed.

continued on next page

Overview of measurement metadata (continued)

Parameter	Unit	Description
TurbIntensity	–	Turbulence intensity at reference height.

SensorConfig.

Internal dataset containing the sensor configuration used during measurement acquisition. It is stored for completeness and traceability but is not further documented, as it is only relevant for internal processing.

WindProfile.

This group contains wind profile measurements which includes datasets for turbulence intensity (Turbulence) and the wind speed profile (WindSpeed) used during preprocessing. Both datasets store meta-data such as the applied approximation formula, least-squares-fitted parameters, reference height, and unit information.

The analysis presented in this report focuses exclusively on the components of the flow along the wind. Raw datasets are also available and stored alongside with this Datapaper to enable further analyzes, for example, of cross-wind components, but they are not evaluated here. The overall data structure follows the schema shown below:

Only the Processed datasets are used for evaluation for the Windprofile; all other datasets are included solely for archiving raw measurement data. The processed datasets follow an alphanumeric naming scheme derived from the mesh generation.

Within each group (PositionName), all relevant data channels are provided. The velocity components UU , VV , WW , and the static pressure PS originate from the original measurements. The derived quantities VEL (global wind speed), $PITCH$, and YAW are computed from these components according to the following relations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 |VEL| &= \sqrt{UU^2 + VV^2 + WW^2} \\
 UU &= \overline{UU} + UU' = |VEL| \cos(PITCH) \cos(YAW) \\
 VV &= \overline{VV} + VV' = |VEL| \cos(PITCH) \sin(YAW) \\
 WW &= \overline{WW} + WW' = |VEL| \sin(PITCH)
 \end{aligned}
 \quad
 \begin{aligned}
 PITCH &= \arcsin\left(\frac{WW}{|VEL|}\right) \\
 YAW &= \arctan\left(\frac{VV}{UU}\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 18 illustrates the flow-axis system with respect to the probe head as well as the definition of positive pitch and yaw angles.

Figure 18: Flow axis system with respect to the Probe head (left). Positive flow pitch and yaw angles (right)

9.3.3. Data Level

The data level is located at the root of the HDF file and contains the measured pressure time series. Datasets are organized hierarchically according to the investigated wind directions and repeated measurements:

```

MeasuredAngle (0–360)
├── MeasurementNumber (0–30)
│   └── TapName
    
```

Each dataset stores the pressure time series of an individual pressure tap for a specific wind direction and measurement run.

10. Data Availability

The datasets described in this paper are openly available via Zenodo as four thematically organized subsets, created to accommodate data volume limitations. The dataset series is published under the title:

A High-Fidelity Dataset of Surface Pressure Measurements on Prismatic Buildings from Boundary-Layer Wind Tunnel Tests

The following subsets constitute the dataset (split due to data limitation):

- Part I – Low-Rise Buildings with Flat Roofs With and Without Parapets
(DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17671165>)
- Part II – Low-Rise Buildings with Mono-Pitched Roofs
(DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17737055>)
- Part III – Low-Rise Buildings with Duo-Pitched Roofs
(DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17737078>)
- Part IV – High-Rise Buildings with Square Cross-Sections and Flat Roofs
(DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17737137>)

Together, these four datasets constitute the complete collection of raw and derived surface pressure measurements described in this paper. The archive contains the full set of raw surface pressure time series, derived statistical quantities, and accompanying metadata describing building geometries, pressure tap layouts, flow conditions, and data processing procedures. The data are released under the Creative Commons Attribution license (CC BY 4.0), permitting unrestricted reuse with appropriate attribution. Users are encouraged to cite the specific subset(s) used in their work, as well as this data paper.

11. Overview of Provided Data

Due to the extensive number of wind tunnel tests performed, this section provides a structured overview of all investigated building models. Table 9 summarizes the complete set of configurations and lists the corresponding references to the appendix, where the characteristic maximum, minimum, and standard deviation of the pressure coefficients are presented for each model.

Table 9: Overview of available models

Model	Roof shape	Parapet ratio	Roof slope	Dimensions	Reference
A0H4W1L1	flat	0	0	4:1:1	A.1
A0H6W1L1	flat	0	0	6:1:1	A.2
A0H8W1L1	flat	0	0	8:1:1	A.3
A0H1L1	flat	0	0	1:2:2	B.1
A0H1L2	flat	0	0	1:2:4	B.2
A0H1L3-edge	flat	0	0	1:2:6	B.3
A0H1L3-center	flat	0	0	1:2:6	B.4
A0H2L1	flat	0	0	2:2:2	B.5
A0H2L2	flat	0	0	2:2:4	B.6
A0H2L3-edge	flat	0	0	2:2:6	B.7
A0H2L3-center	flat	0	0	2:2:6	B.8
A0025H1L1	flat with parapet	0.025	0	1:2:2	C.1
A0025H1L2	flat with parapet	0.025	0	1:2:4	C.2
A0025H1L3-edge	flat with parapet	0.025	0	1:2:6	C.3
A0025H1L3-center	flat with parapet	0.025	0	1:2:6	C.4
A0025H2L1	flat with parapet	0.025	0	2:2:2	C.5
A0025H2L2	flat with parapet	0.025	0	2:2:4	C.6
A0025H2L3-edge	flat with parapet	0.025	0	2:2:6	C.7
A0025H2L3-center	flat with parapet	0.025	0	2:2:6	C.8
A005H1L1	flat with parapet	0.05	0	1:2:2	C.9
A005H1L2	flat with parapet	0.05	0	1:2:4	C.10
A005H1L3-edge	flat with parapet	0.05	0	1:2:6	C.11
A005H1L3-center	flat with parapet	0.05	0	1:2:6	C.12
A005H2L1	flat with parapet	0.05	0	2:2:2	C.13
A005H2L2	flat with parapet	0.05	0	2:2:4	C.14
A005H2L3-edge	flat with parapet	0.05	0	2:2:6	C.15
A005H2L3-center	flat with parapet	0.05	0	2:2:6	C.16
A01H1L1	flat with parapet	0.1	0	1:2:2	C.17
A01H1L2	flat with parapet	0.1	0	1:2:4	C.18
A01H1L3-edge	flat with parapet	0.1	0	1:2:6	C.19
A01H1L3-center	flat with parapet	0.1	0	1:2:6	C.20
A01H2L1	flat with parapet	0.1	0	2:2:2	C.21
A01H2L2	flat with parapet	0.1	0	2:2:4	C.22
A01H2L3-edge	flat with parapet	0.1	0	2:2:6	C.23

Model	Roof shape	Parapet ratio	Roof slope	Dimensions	Reference
A01H2L3-center	flat with parapet	0.1	0	2:2:6	C.24
P5H1L1	mono-pitched	0	5	1:2:2	D.1
P5H1L2	mono-pitched	0	5	1:2:4	D.2
P5H1L3-edge	mono-pitched	0	5	1:2:6	D.3
P5H1L3-center	mono-pitched	0	5	1:2:6	D.4
P5H2L1	mono-pitched	0	5	2:2:2	D.5
P5H2L2	mono-pitched	0	5	2:2:4	D.6
P5H2L3-edge	mono-pitched	0	5	2:2:6	D.7
P5H2L3-center	mono-pitched	0	5	2:2:6	D.8
P10H1L1	mono-pitched	0	10	1:2:2	D.9
P10H1L2	mono-pitched	0	10	1:2:4	D.10
P10H1L3-edge	mono-pitched	0	10	1:2:6	D.11
P10H1L3-center	mono-pitched	0	10	1:2:6	D.12
P10H2L1	mono-pitched	0	10	2:2:2	D.13
P10H2L2	mono-pitched	0	10	2:2:4	D.14
P10H2L3-edge	mono-pitched	0	10	2:2:6	D.15
P10H2L3-center	mono-pitched	0	10	2:2:6	D.16
P15H1L1	mono-pitched	0	15	1:2:2	D.17
P15H1L2	mono-pitched	0	15	1:2:4	D.18
P15H1L3-edge	mono-pitched	0	15	1:2:6	D.19
P15H1L3-center	mono-pitched	0	15	1:2:6	D.20
P15H2L1	mono-pitched	0	15	2:2:2	D.21
P15H2L2	mono-pitched	0	15	2:2:4	D.22
P15H2L3-edge	mono-pitched	0	15	2:2:6	D.23
P15H2L3-center (*)	mono-pitched	0	15	2:2:6	D.24
S5H1L1	duo-pitched	0	5	1:2:2	E.1
S5H1L2	duo-pitched	0	5	1:2:4	E.2
S5H1L3-edge	duo-pitched	0	5	1:2:6	E.3
S5H1L3-center	duo-pitched	0	5	1:2:6	E.4
S5H2L1	duo-pitched	0	5	2:2:2	E.5
S5H2L2	duo-pitched	0	5	2:2:4	E.6
S5H2L3-edge	duo-pitched	0	5	2:2:6	E.7
S5H2L3-center	duo-pitched	0	5	2:2:6	E.8
S10H1L1	duo-pitched	0	10	1:2:2	E.9
S10H1L2	duo-pitched	0	10	1:2:4	E.10
S10H1L3-edge	duo-pitched	0	10	1:2:6	E.11
S10H1L3-center	duo-pitched	0	10	1:2:6	E.12
S10H2L1	duo-pitched	0	10	2:2:2	E.13
S10H2L2	duo-pitched	0	10	2:2:4	E.14
S10H2L3-edge	duo-pitched	0	10	2:2:6	E.15

Model	Roof shape	Parapet ratio	Roof slope	Dimensions	Reference
S10H2L3-center	duo-pitched	0	10	2:2:6	E.16
S15H1L1	duo-pitched	0	15	1:2:2	E.17
S15H1L2	duo-pitched	0	15	1:2:4	E.18
S15H1L3-edge	duo-pitched	0	15	1:2:6	E.19
S15H1L3-center	duo-pitched	0	15	1:2:6	E.20
S15H2L1	duo-pitched	0	15	2:2:2	E.21
S15H2L2	duo-pitched	0	15	2:2:4	E.22
S15H2L3-edge	duo-pitched	0	15	2:2:6	E.23
S15H2L3-center	duo-pitched	0	15	2:2:6	E.24

(*) *Incomplete data-set (some wind directions are missing)*

Appendix A. High-Rise Buildings with Square Cross-Sections and Flat Roofs

Appendix A.1. A0H4W1L1

Figure A.1: Overview of measurement regions and envelope of maximum, minimum and maximum standard deviation of $\bar{c}_{p,10}$ for A0H4W1L1.

Appendix A.2. A0H6W1L1

Figure A.2: Overview of measurement regions and envelope of maximum, minimum of $\bar{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A0H6W1L1.

Appendix A.3. A0H8W1L1

Figure A.3: Overview of measurement regions and envelope of maximum, minimum and maximum standard deviation of $\bar{c}_{p,10}$ for A0H8W1L1.

Appendix B. Low-Rise Buildings with Flat Roofs Without Parapets

Appendix B.1. A0H1

Figure B.1: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A0H1L1.

Figure B.2: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A0H1L2.

Figure B.3: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A0H1L3-edge.

Figure B.4: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A0H1L3-center.

Appendix B.2. A0H2

Figure B.5: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A0H2L1.

Figure B.6: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A0H2L2.

Figure B.7: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A0H2L3-edge.

Figure B.8: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A0H2L3-center.

Appendix C. Low-Rise Buildings with Flat Roofs With Parapets

Appendix C.1. A0025H1

Figure C.1: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A0025H1L1.

Figure C.2: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A0025H1L2.

Figure C.3: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A0025H1L3-edge.

Figure C.4: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A0025H1L3-center.

Appendix C.2. A0025H2

Figure C.5: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A0025H2L1.

Figure C.6: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A0025H2L2.

Figure C.7: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A0025H2L3-edge.

Figure C.8: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A0025H2L3-center.

Appendix C.3. A005H1

Figure C.9: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A005H1L1.

Figure C.10: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A005H1L2.

Figure C.11: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A005H1L3-edge.

Figure C.12: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A005H1L3-center.

Appendix C.4. A005H2

Figure C.13: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A005H2L1.

Figure C.14: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A005H2L2.

Figure C.15: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A005H2L3-edge.

Figure C.16: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A005H2L3-center.

Appendix C.5. A01H1

Figure C.17: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A01H1L1.

Figure C.18: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A01H1L2.

Figure C.19: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A01H1L3-edge.

Figure C.20: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A01H1L3-center.

Appendix C.6. A01H2

Figure C.21: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A01H2L1.

Figure C.22: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A01H2L2.

Figure C.23: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A01H2L3-edge.

Figure C.24: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for A01H2L3-center.

Appendix D. Low-Rise Buildings with Mono-Pitched Roofs

Appendix D.1. P5H1

Figure D.1: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P5H1L1.

Figure D.2: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P5H1L2.

Figure D.3: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P5H1L3-edge.

Figure D.4: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P5H1L3-center.

Appendix D.2. P5H2

Figure D.5: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P5H2L1.

Figure D.6: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P5H2L2.

Figure D.7: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P5H2L3-edge.

Figure D.8: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P5H2L3-center.

Appendix D.3. P10H1

Figure D.9: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P10H1L1.

Figure D.10: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P10H1L2.

Figure D.11: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P10H1L3-edge.

Figure D.12: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P10H1L3-center.

Appendix D.4. P10H2

Figure D.13: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P10H2L1.

Figure D.14: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P10H2L2.

Figure D.15: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P10H2L3-edge.

Figure D.16: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P10H2L3-center.

Appendix D.5. P15H1

Figure D.17: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P15H1L1.

Figure D.18: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P15H1L2.

Figure D.19: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P15H1L3-edge.

Figure D.20: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P15H1L3-center.

Appendix D.6. P15H2

Figure D.21: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P15H2L1.

Figure D.22: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P15H2L2.

Figure D.23: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P15H2L3-edge.

Figure D.24: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for P15H2L3-center.

Appendix E. Low-Rise Buildings with Duo-Pitched Roofs

Appendix E.1. S5H1

Figure E.1: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S5H1L1.

Figure E.2: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S5H1L2.

Figure E.3: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S5H1L3-edge.

Figure E.4: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S5H1L3-center.

Appendix E.2. S5H2

Figure E.5: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S5H2L1.

Figure E.6: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S5H2L2.

Figure E.7: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S5H2L3-edge.

Figure E.8: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S5H2L3-center.

Appendix E.3. S10H1

Figure E.9: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S10H1L1.

Figure E.10: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S10H1L2.

Figure E.11: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S10H1L3-edge.

Figure E.12: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S10H1L3-center.

Appendix E.4. S10H2

Figure E.13: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S10H2L1.

Figure E.14: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S10H2L2.

Figure E.15: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S10H2L3-edge.

Figure E.16: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S10H2L3-center.

Appendix E.5. S15H1

Figure E.17: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S15H1L1.

Figure E.18: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S15H1L2.

Figure E.19: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S15H1L3-edge.

Figure E.20: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S15H1L3-center.

Appendix E.6. S15H2

Figure E.21: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S15H2L1.

Figure E.22: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S15H2L2.

Figure E.23: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S15H2L3-edge.

Figure E.24: Envelope of $\hat{c}_{p,10}$, $\check{c}_{p,10}$ and maximum standard deviation of $c_{p,10}$ for S15H2L3-center.

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